

1 **As psychedelic treatments get leaner, patients' social environments deserve attention**

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4 As psychedelic treatments move toward licensing, clinical intensity is declining, displacing
5 integration work onto patients' social environments. We argue these environments are unmeasured yet
6 plausible moderators of outcome. Supportive contexts may buffer transient distress, while isolating or
7 hostile settings may undermine therapeutic gains. Assessing and strengthening social support through
8 psychoeducation and purpose-built peer infrastructure is therefore a valuable goal for the
9 implementation of these treatments.

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12 As psychedelic treatments edge closer towards licensing, they do so in a form that is meaningfully
13 different to the trials that first captured clinical and public attention. The clinical intensity of these
14 interventions is being progressively reduced: what reaches trial participants is increasingly not
15 'psychedelic-assisted therapy' but 'psychedelics with psychological support'. Though hotly contested
16 (Goodwin et al., 2024,Gründer et al., 2024, Schenberg et al., 2024), the latter framework conceives of
17 the role for the clinician as ensuring safety during drug administration rather than actively facilitating
18 therapeutic change.

19
20 Many forces drive this trajectory: an intuitive tilt towards biological focus in research investigating
21 pharmacological agents; the need to make the treatment package more legible to regulators
22 accustomed to evaluating drugs, not complex psychosocial interventions; or the need for scalable
23 treatment models that can be made broadly accessible. Regardless of the rationale, as recent
24 conceptual work makes clear (Schettino et al., 2025), the difference between *psychedelic-assisted*
25 *therapy* and psychedelics with *psychological support* is consequential - not least in the phase formerly
26 known as *integration*. Meeting again with therapists in the days and weeks following a psychedelic
27 experience, patients had an opportunity to explore at length the significance of visions, emotions, and
28 the varied psychological material that arose during acute drug effects. The emotional breakthroughs
29 that occur during acute drug effects, and the psychological insights they can catalyse in the days and
30 weeks that follow - both predictors of therapeutic benefit (Roseman et al., 2019; Peill et al., 2022) -
31 could be held and worked through with a skilled clinician, and the 'landing' back to everyday life
32 could be softened.

33
34 Integration provides a supportive, non-judgmental space to explore this material, to settle transient
35 psychological distress or disturbance that some patients can experience after a psychedelic trip, and
36 provides an opportunity for all patients to conceive, concretely, how to integrate what they've learned
37 into meaningful and lasting positive changes in their lives. As leaner models progressively cut down
38 on clinical contact, the psychological functions that this contact performed - processing,
39 consolidation, support through transient disturbance - do not evaporate. They are displaced elsewhere,
40 or otherwise go unfulfilled. Whether these functions are safety- or efficacy-related, better
41 understanding the compensation that does (or does not) happen is an important goal for psychedelic
42 science.

43 44 ***Social environment as unexamined moderator***

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46 Where clinical contact is reduced, this work falls to other elements in the patient's social
47 environments. In many cases, this can suffice - the emotional and cognitive processing of a

1 psychedelic experience, its significance to a patient's ill-health and self-understanding, can be
2 undertaken in concert with those who know them the best, and care for them the most.

3
4 But social environments vary enormously in their ability to support such functions. While social
5 support counts among the highest-endorsed coping strategies for those experiencing post-psychedelic
6 difficulties, not all social environments are equal (Robinson et al., 2024). For patients returning from
7 psychedelic treatment to isolation, dismissive relationships, or communities that stigmatise
8 psychedelic use, the reduction in clinical contact may be more keenly felt.

9
10 There remains substantial unexplained variance in outcomes from psychedelic treatments. The
11 qualities of the social environments patients return to is a credible candidate contributor - but one that
12 cannot be evaluated because it remains unassessed. It would hardly be surprising were patients' social
13 environments to exert some influence on therapeutic trajectories following psychedelic treatments --
14 social environments exert influence on therapeutic trajectories across all manner of mental health
15 conditions and treatment modalities (Zell and Stockus, 2025; Carter et al., 2012; Ma et al., 2021).
16 There is little reason to think that psychedelic treatments would be exempt from this pattern, though
17 the magnitude of the impact is an open empirical question.

18
19 However, the psychedelic-enhanced plasticity of mind, brain and behaviour frequently offered as an
20 explanation for these compounds' transdiagnostic effects gives grounds to take the prospect seriously.
21 Such plasticity is valence-neutral: a period of heightened environmental sensitivity is liable to lend
22 outsized influence to a patient's post-psychedelic environment. But our argument does not rest on this
23 mechanism alone. The pragmatic claim, that reducing clinical contact displaces integration functions
24 onto unmeasured and unsupported social environments, holds regardless of whether psychedelics
25 amplify environmental influence. Whether they do is a testable hypothesis.

26
27 It is well-established that patients can experience challenges returning to their lives after even
28 successful treatments. Successful treatment for serious illness can itself generate psychosocial
29 difficulties that existing support systems can be unprepared for - consider the 'burden of normality'
30 and renegotiation of social identity when the 'sick role' is laid down after successful epilepsy surgery
31 (Wilson et al., 2001), or 're-entry' challenges after cancer treatment (King et al., 2023; Zarei et al.,
32 2025). A substantial literature has demonstrated poorer psychosocial outcomes for cancer patients
33 who feel constrained from voicing their thoughts and feelings about their cancer to those close to
34 them (Adams, Winger and Mosher, 2015). When people feel constrained from sharing what's on their
35 mind, it can disrupt processing of challenging experiences, prolong intrusive thoughts, increase
36 avoidance, and ultimately worsen adjustment (Lepore and Revenson, 2007). A psychedelic experience
37 undertaken in a clinical trial has little in common with cancer, of course. But both are experienced as
38 significant events that can disrupt people's core beliefs about themselves and their wider worlds - and
39 both can require cognitive and emotional processing: making sense of, habituating to, and integrating
40 the implications of what has been experienced.

41
42 What people return to after their psychedelic experience does seem to shape what follows. Patients in
43 psilocybin trials who lacked strong social support described feeling vulnerable and isolated after
44 treatment (Watts et al., 2017); retreat attendees returning to psychedelic-naive communities describe
45 're-entry' challenges (Cowley-Court et al., 2023; Lutkajtis and Evans, 2023); and in one ethnographic
46 study of a community integration group, participants described challenging experiences reinterpreted
47 constructively through ongoing peer dialogue (Gezon, 2025).

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1 Similar patterns have emerged in our own observations across diverse roles and contexts: as
2 researcher, as trial participant and patient advocate, as dosing session facilitator, and integration
3 practitioner. Consistent with stress-buffering models of social support (Cohen and Wills, 1985), such
4 support seems to function less as a constant benefit, and more as a resource critically mobilised under
5 strain. The transient psychological disturbance that some patients experience after psychedelic
6 administration is one such moment of strain, and even when treatment succeeds at symptom
7 reduction, it can generate "new problems and riddles" unrelated to clinical targets (Noorani, 2020):
8 shifts in perspective, relational re-evaluation, existential re-orientation. Some social environments
9 have the capacity to support the processing of these demands. Others do not, and it is here that the
10 reduction of clinical contact is liable to matter most.

11

12 These findings and observations span naturalistic and clinical contexts of various stripes. Their
13 convergence suggests that the need for social support following psychedelic experiences is driven not
14 by features of a particular use context, but by features of the experience itself: its intensity, its
15 personal or spiritual significance, its capacity to challenge established self-understanding. These same
16 features likely contribute to symptom reduction, which makes supporting patients through them all the
17 more important.

18

19 *Preparing existing support*

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21 The most immediately actionable response is to equip those most invested in the patient's recovery
22 and enduring benefit - partners, family members, close friends - with the understanding and
23 confidence to provide effective support. Developing more structured and detailed psychoeducation for
24 families, to be delivered before treatment, can equip supporters to respond proportionately to
25 emotional disturbances rather than catastrophising, and to recognise that shifts in how patients see
26 themselves, their relationships, or their priorities may be part of the therapeutic process rather than
27 new symptoms. Such psychoeducation has been trialled in some studies, and preliminary evidence
28 suggests it can be valued highly (Beckley Psytech & PsyPAN, 2024). However, the success of such
29 psychoeducation assumes reasonably receptive, emotionally close relationships, and a family or
30 relational system with the flexibility and emotional resources to respond. Psychoeducation cannot
31 create support networks that do not yet exist, nor overcome resistance or lack of engagement from
32 partners, families, or communities. For patients whose social environments are characterised by
33 isolation, instability, or hostility towards psychedelic treatment, preparation of the existing network is
34 insufficient. Something else is needed.

35

36 *Building compensatory infrastructure*

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38 Where existing relationships cannot provide what integration requires, the natural response is to look
39 beyond them. Compensatory support infrastructure offers a viable alternative: structured opportunities
40 for connection with others who can provide what the immediate social environment cannot. Peer
41 support and group-based integration groups offer something structurally different from both one-on-
42 one clinical contact and well-meaning but psychedelic-naive loved ones: the felt sense of being seen
43 and understood by someone navigating similar psychological terrain - the 'fellow traveller' role
44 recognised across post-treatment support in oncology, bereavement, and other fields (Bartone et al.,
45 2019; Zhang et al., 2022, Joo et al., 2022). One study of post-psychedelic challenges found that the
46 most frequently endorsed forms of helpful support were feeling heard, acceptance, and shared
47 experience (Robinson et al., 2024) precisely what peer networks are distinctively positioned to
48 provide.

1
2 Early research into such groups provide promising signals (Modlin et al., 2025, Gezon, 2025), though
3 the integration groups of various formats already operating across the psychedelic ecosystem (Cheung
4 et al., 2024) are rarely designed for clinical populations. Participant advocacy work and our own
5 clinical observation suggest that groups primarily catering to recreational or retreat users can make for
6 an uneasy fit. Though all participants share the experience of processing a psychedelic journey, the
7 trajectory of someone treating chronic illness in a clinical trial differs meaningfully from that of a
8 recreational or retreat user. Trial participants have described their clinical trial context being met with
9 fascination rather than fellow-feeling, their sense of isolation reproduced rather than resolved - *you go*
10 *seeking peers, and find yourself a specimen.*

11
12 As such, compensatory infrastructure might be fruitfully purpose-built for clinical populations.
13 Purpose-built groups eliminate the cumulative burden of translation: what it means to live with a
14 chronic illness, to participate in a clinical trial, and to have received a psychedelic with a specific hope
15 of recovery. These are layers of difference that each require effort to bridge; assuming shared
16 understanding removes that burden. Such purpose built programmes are beginning to emerge (for
17 transparency, two of the authorship team have developed such models), and formal evaluation is
18 underway.

19 20 ***Moving forward***

21
22 At the very least, research protocols should incorporate measures of patients' social and relational
23 environments. Validated instruments for assessing a range of plausible environmental moderators of
24 outcome trajectories exist, and could, in the first instance, be used without developing new measures.

25
26 Testing whether, e.g., social support, social constraint, or family functioning explains meaningful
27 variance in outcomes beyond established predictors is important for gaining clarity in the debate about
28 clinical intensity. If supportive social environments absorb what clinical contact previously provided,
29 while less supportive environments leave those functions unfulfilled, aggregate analyses that ignore
30 this variable will make clinical support appear inert when it is actually conditionally necessary. Such
31 an interaction may be *particularly* difficult to detect in current trial samples, which substantially
32 overrepresent well-educated and financially secure populations (Grossman et al., 2025) - groups most
33 likely to possess the social capital and material resources that we believe are among the buffers to
34 integration challenges. If such an interaction does exist, then treatment effect sizes - and adverse event
35 rates - reported in extant psychedelic trials may not generalise to the broader and more
36 socioeconomically diverse populations that we hope these treatments will ultimately be made
37 available to.

38
39 And we do hope that these treatments become widely available and accessible options. Should our
40 reasoning here be confirmed empirically - i.e., that treatment outcomes are meaningfully moderated
41 by social and relational environment - pre-treatment assessment of unfavourable social and relational
42 environment (however that is ultimately operationalised) should by default to serve as an indicator for
43 enhanced support, rather than as exclusionary screen.

44
45 The considerations above are sharpest for patients whose environments are least supportive and least
46 malleable. Happily, many patients are able to actively restructure their social environments after
47 psychedelic treatment, perhaps buoyed by the immediate biological antidepressant and behaviourally
48 activating qualities of the drug. Such patients seek out new, nourishing relationships, refresh and

1 reinvest in existing ties, renegotiate complicated but valued connections, and withdraw from toxic or
2 harmful ones. But the capacity to do this is not evenly distributed - among other factors, it can be
3 dependent on social capital, relational flexibility, and financial stability. For the patients trapped by
4 financial dependence, coercive dynamics, or the sheer depletion that chronic illness imposes on the
5 capacity to seek and maintain emotionally nourishing connections, an instruction to simply 'build
6 better support' would be functionally empty.

7
8 The marginal cost of the measures we have called for (expanded familial psychoeducation, structured
9 peer-support or group integration) is modest relative to the per-participant cost of treatment itself: an
10 incremental investment amenable to philanthropic support. Evaluated alongside clinical outcomes,
11 such provision would do double duty: addressing participants' expressed needs while generating
12 evidence on integration practice that the field will need as these treatments approach implementation
13 (Jacobs et al., 2024). While we consider these measures a credible prospect for improving clinical
14 outcomes and safety, we will close with a simpler observation: the post-psychedelic period is one in
15 which users express that they want to feel heard, have their experience validated, and to make sense of
16 what they've gone through alongside others who understand. These are not clinimetric outcomes.
17 They are human needs. The evidence base for psychedelic treatments has been built on the
18 willingness of participants to undergo these experiences; ensuring that what follows those experiences
19 is adequately supported seems a modest return on that contribution. Building infrastructure that
20 addresses these needs while generating data on clinical impact is a more defensible course of action
21 than withholding support pending definitive proof of efficacy.

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